

Cover Letter

The present manuscript submitted for your approval is entitled: **Histological examinations of the mycelium and spores of taro leaf blight pathogen (*Phytophthora colocasiae* Racib.)**

Taro (*Colocasia esculenta*) is a tuber crop with medicinal, food and industrial properties. However, its production continues to be severely disrupted by an oomycete: *Phytophthora colocasiae* (*P. colocasiae*). In production areas around the world, and particularly in Cameroon, we are increasingly witnessing a drastic reduction in production yields and a consequent shortage of crops on the market. This problem raises questions about the effectiveness of the control approach in place. The chemicals and fungicides used to control the disease are resistant to the pathogen. Varieties that are considered to be resistant or less susceptible to the disease are attacked in the fields. As for the recommended cultural practices, they do not make it possible to remedy the situation. In order to make this control approach more effective or to establish more relevant ones, we believe that it is necessary to focus more on the biology of *P. colocasiae* (we are in a changing world and *Phytophthora* species are known as species with great evolutionary potential), because they will provide useful data for its control. Although information on the biology of *P. colocasiae* is available, the following hypotheses motivated the orientation of our approach:

- 1) Each living organism has its own genetic material that defines its identity.
- 2) They are susceptible to evolution as a result of climatic changes, their interaction with their environment and the host's response during infection.
- 3) This evolution can lead to the addition of new elements to the pathogen's biological cycle, polymorphism, the formation of new morphotypes with more virulent strains resistant to fungicides, the formation of new species and the modification of the interaction with the host.

We were therefore interested in the different stages of formation and fate of the mycelial form of the pathogen, as it is involved in the nutrition, infection, growth, reproduction and spread of *P. colocasiae*. Using phytopathological techniques (identification of the botanical sample at the National Herbarium of Cameroon, isolation, pathogenicity test and culture in liquid medium), histology (obtaining thin sections of the mycelium after conventional treatment) and microscopy (visualisation), we obtained the following results:

- 1) The biological material was collected and analysed according to the national requirements mentioned in the Order N° 0072/MINADER/SG/DRCQ/SDRSQV of 22 April 2019, establishing procedures for the recognition of species and varieties. **The botanical sample was identified and confirmed as *Colocasiae esculenta* (L.) schott (Araceae) at the National Herbarium of Cameroon** by Mr. NGANSOP T. Eric, Botanist, Systematist and Taxonomist, in comparison with the original material of the National Herbarium N° 42359/HNC collected by Westphal under N° 10085.

2) The mycelium of *P. colocasiae* is gradually formed by the progressive elongation of the thallus, which becomes interwoven (Figure 3). This is followed by the formation of sporangiospores from which the sporangia detach and finally the formation of chlamydospores (Figure 5).

This information is available on the life cycle of *P. colocasiae*. However, it was necessary to illustrate it before moving on to the new elements that appear to be relevant to the biology of the pathogen.

3) We identified the apical body (Figure 4). It is a vegetative structure that is considered to be the engine of mycelial growth in microscopic fungi in general.

- The biological cycle of *P. colocasiae* does not mention this structure and very few scientific articles on *P. colocasiae* talk about it.

- The available research on the biosynthesis of the apical body of filamentous fungi shows that it is formed by actin polymerisation. It is therefore likely to have a different hyphal structure. Control methods should take this into account. For example, will a fungicide applied at a certain concentration to the leaf surface to inhibit pathogen growth have the same effect on the hyphae as on the apical body? If so, at the same concentration?

➤ In terms of perspective, control methods should specifically target the apical body.

4) The study also showed the formation of several spores of different morphology and size (Figure 6).

In the current state of knowledge, the biological cycle of *P. colocasiae* refers to two types of spores: zoospores, which are asexual spores, and oospores, which are sexual spores.

Thus, the different morphology of the spores obtained in our study is not mentioned in the biological cycle of *P. colocasiae* and very few studies on the pathogen discuss it.

➤ In perspectives:

- These spores of different morphologies would be produced by the pathogen to cope with difficult environmental conditions (resistance mechanism).

- Will a fungicide necessarily have the same effect on each of these spores? If so, at the same concentration?

- Will a so-called resistant or less susceptible variety of taro necessarily retain its ability to resist each of these spores?

5) Among the spores observed and shown in Figure 6, some have a morphology similar to oospores (sexual spores).

The experiments were carried out on a pure culture (a single isolate). Therefore, based on current knowledge of *P. colocasiae*, we should have asexual reproduction resulting in zoospores only (asexual spores). This result raises questions about the heterothallism of *P. colocasiae*. In fact, we should not get oospores from asexual reproduction.

➤ Perspectives:

- Heterothallism is determined by genes. What is the determinism of their expression?
- Sexual spores are also produced during asexual reproduction (evolution or resistance mechanism)?
- Although *P. colocasiae* is known to be a heterothallic species, previous work has identified some self-fertile isolates (capable of producing oospores in pure culture).

6) The present work also illustrates the behaviour of the spores: some of them approach each other, stick together and fuse (Figure 7).

- This dynamic between spores does not occur in the biological cycle of *P. colocasiae*. Nor are we aware of any scientific publications that illustrate it.
- This result would have an impact on the ploidy of the vegetative structure resulting from the fusion of the spores.
- At present we know that *P. colocasiae* spores are diploid. What would be the ploidy of the structure resulting from the fusion of two diploid spores? diploid, triploid or tetraploid?
- Will a possible change in ploidy have an impact on pathogenesis?
- The result obtained in our study would explain the triploid and tetraploid strains of *P. colocasiae* identified by the researchers.
- During the fusion of the spores, we observe plasmogamy (fusion of the cytoplasm), as shown in Figure 7C. This plasmogamy should lead to an interaction between the two genetic materials and be at the origin of; new morphotypes, polymorphism, mutations.

➤ Perspectives:

- Could this fusion of spores be used by the pathogen to face difficult environmental conditions (resistance mechanism)?
- Would a fungicide at the same concentration necessarily have the same effect on single spores as on fused spores?

7) Since the mechanism of sexual reproduction in *P. colocasia* is known, the observed spore fusion would be an illustration of a parasexual mechanism or somatic fusion. Very few studies on *P. colocasia* discuss this with illustrations.

In conclusion, we believe that the present work provides data necessary for understanding the biology of *P. colocasia*, unless it is better appreciated by your experts and reviewers. These data should be taken into account when developing strategies for disease control.

- In perspective, we plan to carry out the formulation of plant extracts that can prevent the formation of the apical body (inhibition of actin polymerisation), but also to carry out molecular and cellular analyses to evaluate the genetic and structural impact of spore fusion on the resulting vegetative structure.

Indeed, the observed fusion of the spores raises questions:

What is the new structural organisation of the resulting entity?

- Do the organelles fuse?
- Do the nuclei fuse? If we obtain a dikaryon, what is the nucleus that will control the functioning of the cell?
- Each spore contributes its chromosomes to the resulting structure. If the number of chromosomes increases, is it still the same species?
- Can this fusion be considered as a mechanism of speciation?

In addition, we believe that the subject matter covered falls within the scope of your journal.

We confirm that neither the manuscript nor any part of it is currently under consideration or has been published in another journal.

All authors have approved the manuscript and agree to its submission.

(<https://zenodo.org/uploads/13630406>)

We remain at your disposal to provide any additional information you may require.

Yours sincerely,